

DRAFT REPORT: Harmonizing Meta- data Across Helmholtz Infrastructures

Community Perspectives & Next Steps — Kickoff Workshop Report, 19 February 2026

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1 Executive Summary

1.1 English

Improving the interoperability of academic publication metadata across large, distributed research infrastructures requires not only technical standardization but sustained community engagement and institutional alignment. This report documents the methodology, findings, and recommendations arising from the “Harmonizing Metadata Across Helmholtz Infrastructures” kick-off workshop and an accompanying metadata gap analysis, both conducted as part of the [Helmholtz Metadata Collaboration \(HMC\)](#) program.

Publication metadata across Helmholtz flows through a diverse landscape of institutional repositories. While this enables broad access to research outputs, structural differences, inconsistent terminology, and incomplete records limit interoperability and hinder services like the [FAIR Data Dashboard](#) and the [Helmholtz KG](#). To understand these variations and engage data providers, TF Harmony adopted a dual approach: quantitative analysis followed by community consultation.

As a first step, an initial metadata gap analysis was conducted to identify recurring patterns in how publication metadata is structured across Helmholtz infrastructures. A quantitative gap analysis of approximately three million OAI-PMH records assessed field-level consistency across `dc:type`, `dc:identifier`, and `dc:date`, revealed widespread heterogeneity in date formatting and persistent identifier usage. The analysis showed that, although key metadata elements are often present, important differences remain in completeness, standardization, and semantic consistency. Building on these observations, a community workshop was held on 19 February 2026, bringing together representatives from Helmholtz data providers and repository teams. It convened more than fifty stakeholders from 17 of 18 Helmholtz centers, including repository managers, data stewards, and infrastructure leads, to identify practical barriers and priorities for metadata harmonization. The workshop combined presentations of HMC services and analytical findings with structured breakout discussions. These discussions were designed to capture participants’ perspectives on current metadata practices, including perceived constraints, semantic challenges, and expectations regarding HMC support. The thematic analysis of breakout discussions revealed that participants’ challenges extend beyond technical implementation to encompass organizational contexts, resource constraints, and differing interpretations of metadata standards. Specific constraints include limited resources, legacy system dependencies, and institutional culture. Participants consistently preferred differentiated, center-specific support over prescriptive standards, reflecting the diversity of contexts across the Helmholtz community. These findings, while representing workshop participants rather than a comprehensive survey, provide useful indications of recurring themes across infrastructures. Together, the gap analysis and community input suggest that improving publication metadata and interoperability requires approaches addressing both technical and contextual factors. HMC plans to continue this work through individualized consulting sessions with data providers, ongoing metadata analysis, and a follow-up workshop to share aggregated insights and discuss next steps.

1.2 German

Die Verbesserung der Interoperabilität von akademischen Publikationsmetadaten in großen, verteilten Forschungsinfrastrukturen erfordert nicht nur technische Standardisierung, sondern auch kontinuierliches Community-Engagement und institutionelle Ausrichtung. Dieser Bericht dokumentiert die Methodik, die Ergebnisse und die Empfehlungen aus dem Kick-off-Workshop „Harmonizing Metadata Across Helmholtz Infrastructures“ und einer begleitenden Metadaten-Lückenanalyse, die beide im Rahmen des [Helmholtz Metadata Collaboration \(HMC\)](#)-Programms durchgeführt wurden.

Publikationsmetadaten in Helmholtz fließen durch eine vielfältige Landschaft institutioneller Repositorien. Während dies einen breiten Zugang zu Forschungsergebnissen ermöglicht, schränken strukturelle Unterschiede, inkonsistente Terminologie und unvollständige Datensätze die Interoperabilität ein und beeinträchtigen Dienste wie das [FAIR Data Dashboard](#) und den [Helmholtz KG](#). Um diese Variationen zu verstehen und Datenanbieter einzubeziehen, hat TF Harmony einen dualen Ansatz verfolgt: quantitative Analyse gefolgt von Community-Konsultation.

Als erster Schritt wurde eine erste Metadaten-Lückenanalyse durchgeführt, um zu ermitteln, wie Publikationsmetadaten über Helmholtz-Infrastrukturen strukturiert sind, und wiederkehrende Muster zu identifizieren. Eine quantitative Lückenanalyse von ungefähr drei Millionen OAI-PMH-Datensätzen bewertete die Feldkonsistenz über dc:type, dc:identifier und dc:date hinweg und ergab eine weit verbreitete Heterogenität bei der Datumsformatierung und der Verwendung persistenter Identifikatoren. Die Analyse zeigte, dass obwohl wichtige Metadatenelemente oft vorhanden sind, wichtige Unterschiede in Bezug auf Vollständigkeit, Standardisierung und semantische Konsistenz bestehen bleiben.

Aufbauend auf diesen Beobachtungen wurde am 19. Februar 2026 ein Community-Workshop veranstaltet, der Vertreterinnen der *Helmholtz-Datenanbieter und Repository-Teams zusammenbrachte*. *Es nahmen mehr als fünfzig Beteiligte aus 17 von 18 Helmholtz-Zentren teil, darunter Repository-Managerinnen, Datenstewards und Infrastrukturverantwortliche*, um praktische Hindernisse und Prioritäten für die Metadaten-Harmonisierung zu identifizieren.

Der Workshop kombinierte Präsentationen von HMC-Diensten und analytischen Ergebnissen mit strukturierten Breakout-Diskussionen. Diese Diskussionen sollten die Perspektiven der Teilnehmer*innen zu aktuellen Metadatenpraktiken erfassen, einschließlich wahrgenommener Einschränkungen, semantischer Herausforderungen und Erwartungen bezüglich der HMC-Unterstützung.

Die thematische Analyse der Breakout-Diskussionen ergab, dass die Herausforderungen der Teilnehmer über die technische Implementierung hinausgehen und organisatorische Kontexte, Ressourcenbeschränkungen und unterschiedliche Interpretationen von Metadatenstandards umfassen. Spezifische Einschränkungen umfassen begrenzte Ressourcen, Abhängigkeiten von Legacy-Systemen und institutionelle Kultur. Die Teilnehmer bevorzugten konsequent eine differenzierte, -zentrum-spezifische Unterstützung gegenüber preskriptiven Standards, was die

Vielfalt der Kontexte in der Helmholtz-Community widerspiegelt. Diese Ergebnisse repräsentieren zwar die Workshop-Teilnehmer und keine umfassende Erhebung, liefern aber nützliche Hinweise auf wiederkehrende Themen über Infrastrukturen hinweg.

Zusammengenommen deuten die Lückenanalyse und die Community-Inputs darauf hin, dass die Verbesserung von Publikationsmetadaten und Interoperabilität Ansätze erfordert, die sowohl technische als auch kontextuelle Faktoren berücksichtigen. HMC plant, diese Arbeit durch individualisierte Beratungssitzungen mit Datenanbietern, kontinuierliche nMetadatenanalyse und einen Follow-up-Workshop fortzusetzen, um aggregierte Erkenntnisse auszutauschen und mögliche nächste Schritte zu diskutieren.

2 Background and Context

Within the Helmholtz Association, the Helmholtz Metadata Collaboration (HMC) is part of the Helmholtz Incubator Framework for Information and Data Science. [Helmholtz Association \[2016\]](#) The mission of HMC is to facilitate the discovery, access, machine readability, and reuse of the Helmholtz Association's research data. As such HMC develops and provides services that increase metadata visibility, support metadata quality assessment, and enable the integration of metadata across the Helmholtz Association's distributed infrastructures.

The Helmholtz Association is Germany's largest research performing organisation and comprises 18 independent centers distributed geographically across Germany. These centers design and maintain large-scale infrastructures which help address the big questions of our time across 6 research fields. Underpinning these centers and infrastructures is a vast information ecosystem. HMC's vision is to transform this ecosystem into a FAIR (findable, accessible, interoperable, reusable) data space, in line with broader concepts of interoperable data spaces. [Wilkinson et al. \[2016\]](#), [Nagel and Lycklama \[2022\]](#)

HMC services, such as the Dashboard on Open and FAIR Data in Helmholtz (FAIR Data Dashboard), [Kubin et al. \[2024\]](#) which supports the assessment of metadata quality and FAIRness, and the Helmholtz KG, [Helmholtz Metadata Collaboration \[2026\]](#) which enables centralized searchability and linking of research outputs across Helmholtz infrastructures, illustrate the fundamental challenges in achieving this vision. Both services harvest metadata from diverse provider systems and bring it together in shared environments to improve findability, comparability, and reuse. Their impact depends on the availability and consistency of source metadata - in other words, on how consistently core information is structured, expressed, and maintained within and across provider systems. This problem is not only technical but also social. It depends on local practices, responsibilities, and constraints across the diverse infrastructures present in Helmholtz.

To address these technical and social aspects together HMC created the TF Harmony in September 2025. The task force has the following aims: to create a forum for exchange with current and potential data providers to HMC services; identify, analyse and raise awareness of common metadata problems; and provide individual counselling for providers to solve these

3.1 Selection of Priority Fields

From these metadata formats, we chose oai_dc for our analysis, as it is the only format mandated by the OAI-PMH harvesting protocol and therefore available on every endpoint. This ensures comparability between results while keeping the analysis concise.

Based on qualitative feedback from the FAIR Data Dashboard and Helmholtz KG teams we then further narrowed our focus to three core metadata fields:

- Resource type: dc:type
- Identifier: dc: identifier
- Publication year: dc:date.

The FAIR Data Dashboard and Helmholtz KG teams highlighted that these fields are crucial for finding, identifying, and classifying metadata records in a federated research infrastructure. Qualitatively they indicated that they regularly encounter problems in these records from the information they harvest. Harmonising their implementation would directly impact the quality of service that the Helmholtz KG and FAIR Data Dashboard could offer. More broadly, studying their implementation provided a practical entry point for examining broader issues such as the use of controlled vocabularies, persistent identifiers, and standardized date formats.

Our examination followed the following steps: - determine if the field exists in the metadata record or not - take steps to establish the validity of the information contained in the field.

3.2 Resource Identifier

The dc: identifier field plays a central role in distinguishing one metadata record from another. Conceptually, it provides the basis for unambiguous reference, linking, and retrieval across systems, and is therefore essential for identification and interoperability. In the analyzed corpus, all 3 million metadata records contain at least one dc: identifier field. In this sense, field presence is complete. With regard to representation, dc: identifier values appear in two main forms. In 93% of records, the field contains a Uniform Resource Identifier (URI), while in 7% it contains a plain string. From the perspective of quality and standardization, the key issue is not only whether an identifier is present, but whether it is persistent and globally interpretable. Ideally, dc: identifier should contain a Persistent Identifier (PID), since only PIDs support stable and unambiguous identification across infrastructures. Of the URIs found in dc: identifier, 6% are DOIs, which represent one specific type of PID.

These observations show that identifier fields are widely present, but that persistence and standardized identifier practice remain uneven. This matters because the mere existence of an identifier does not guarantee reliable linking, reuse, or cross-system integration.

Left: Data types of `dc:identifier`.

Right: DOI share of all URIs in `dc:identifier`.

Figure 2: Resource identifier analysis.

3.3 Resource Type

The `dc:type` field classifies the kind, or type, of resource described by the metadata record. This field supports filtering, aggregation, and interpretation by indicating whether a record refers to an article, thesis, dataset, or another type of research output. In terms of completeness, `dc:type` is present in nearly all records. In less than 1% of records, the field is missing.

With regard to representation, values occur either as URIs or as free-text. In 86% of cases, `dc:type` values are URIs (e.g., `info:eu-repo/semantics/article` or `doc-type:bachelorThesis`), while 13% are free-text (e.g., `Thesis`, `Article`, `Book`). The remaining share is negligible.

From the perspective of quality and standardization, URI-based values from controlled vocabularies are preferable to free-text because they support consistent and machine-readable classification. An analysis of the URI schemes shows that 94% originate from the `info` namespace, 5% from `doc-type`, and 1% from other HTTPS URIs (e.g., `https://purl.org/dc/dcmitype/Dataset`). Using controlled vocabularies such as [info:eu-repo](https://www.euro.ox.ac.uk/info:eu-repo) or [COAR](https://www.coar-repo.org/) improves semantic clarity and interoperability.

These observations show that `dc:type` is generally well populated, but that a notable share of records still relies on uncontrolled free-text values. This matters because ambiguous or locally specific type descriptions reduce comparability across infrastructures and complicate consistent classification in downstream services.

Left: Data types of `dc:type`.

Right: Share of URI schemes in `dc:type`.

Figure 3: Resource type analysis.

3.4 Resource Publication Date

The `dc:date` field records the publication date of the described resource. Conceptually, this field supports temporal filtering, sorting, contextualization, and the interpretation of research outputs over time. Standardized date information is also important for machine readability and interoperable processing. Compared with the other two priority fields, `dc:date` shows the greatest weaknesses in completeness. In 50% of all records the field is missing entirely. Where the field is present, values appear in different date formats. In 38% of all records, `dc:date` contains values that are compliant with ISO 8601 [International Organization for Standardization \[2019\]](#) (for example, 2003-10-22), while 12% contain values that are not ISO-compliant (for example, 1953-1959). Date representations therefore vary substantially across records.

From the perspective of quality and standardization, this variation is significant. While humans can often interpret a wide range of date expressions, machine-readable integration depends on consistent formatting. ISO 8601 is the most widely used standard for date representation and provides a common basis for interoperable date processing.

These observations show that `dc:date` is the weakest of the three analyzed fields in both completeness and standardization. This matters because missing or inconsistently formatted dates limit filtering, temporal interpretation, and reliable reuse across infrastructures.

Left: Date standard of `dc:date`.

Right: ISO 8601 format distribution of `dc:date`.

Figure 4: Resource publication date analysis.

3.5 Summary

These observations indicated that metadata harmonization is not only a technical issue, but also one that requires exchange with the people and teams responsible for creating, managing, and exposing metadata in practice.

The `dc:identifier` field is consistently present across all records. With 93% of identifiers expressed as URIs, the potential for unique identification is high, although not guaranteed. Efforts should therefore focus on increasing the share of persistent identifiers (PIDs), such as DOIs, across all records.

In the case of `dc:type`, 13% of values are still expressed as free-text, indicating considerable use of uncontrolled vocabulary. Reducing this share is important to improve interoperability within the Helmholtz data space. At the same time, the majority of URI-based values are well standardized and largely aligned with the `info` namespace.

The `dc:date` field exhibits the most significant deficiencies in both completeness and standardization. Half of the records lack date information altogether, and only 38% are standardized according to ISO 8601. As standardized formats are essential for machine readability and, therefore, for interoperability, measures should be taken not only to ensure publication dates for all records, but also their compliance with ISO 8601.

This analysis showed that differences exist across infrastructures: identifiers are widely present, but persistent identifiers are not used consistently; resource types are often well structured, yet free-text values remain; publication dates contain many missing values and inconsistent formatting. Importantly, they provide a narrow set of issues, relevant to a broad audience which could provide the starting point for the workshop discussions.

The goal was not only to show where metadata gaps appear in the records, but also to explore why they occur in practice and what kinds of support may help address them.

4 Workshop Design and Data Collection

4.1 Workshop Context

The workshop was designed to generate structured community input on current metadata practices across Helmholtz infrastructures. In addition to presenting relevant HMC services and the initial metadata gap analysis, it created a space for participants to reflect on institutional constraints, semantic challenges, and expectations regarding metadata harmonization and HMC support.

- **Title:** [Harmonizing Metadata Across Helmholtz Infrastructures: Community Perspectives & Next Steps](#)
- **Date & Time:** 19 February 2026, 09:30–12:30
- **Format:** Online
- **Participants:** Representatives from 17 of 18 Helmholtz centers, as well as external metadata organizations, with more than 50 participants attending overall.

4.2 Workshop Participants

Each data source harvested by HMC infrastructure was identified. The majority of these data sources provide e-mail addresses for support in the APIs they provide. An invitation email was sent to these functional email addresses. In the case where an email wasn't provided by the API an alternative functional email address, or online help form was found. This was successful at recruiting the target audience to participate in the event with representatives from infrastructures at 17 of 18 Helmholtz centers registering to attend the event.

In addition the event was posted once on HMC social media channels (LinkedIn, Mastodon, Bluesky). The event page was publically accessible and visible.

4.3 Workshop Structure

The workshop combined short input presentations with structured discussion. Initial presentations introduced relevant HMC services and summarized key findings from the metadata gap analysis. These inputs were followed by breakout discussions and plenary synthesis, generating the qualitative material used in the subsequent analysis.

More specifically, the workshop opened with a short welcome and framing of the session goals, followed by an overview of HMC harvesting-related services and the role of publication metadata in the FAIR Data Dashboard and the Helmholtz KG. The gap analysis findings then provided a shared analytical starting point for discussion. In the interactive part of the workshop, participants reflected on current metadata practices, institutional constraints, semantic challenges, and expectations regarding HMC support. A final plenary segment was used to synthesize recurring themes across groups and to outline next steps for continued exchange.

4.4 Initial Polls

At the beginning of the workshop, two short polls were conducted to capture participants' **self-reported practices and familiarity** with HMC harvesting approaches. The results provide context for interpreting the subsequent discussions, particularly regarding awareness and perceived capabilities.

Poll 1: *Which harvesting interfaces does your organisation currently expose?* (multiple choice)

The responses indicate that OAI-PMH is recognized by a majority of participants as an exposed interface. However, a notable share of respondents reported uncertainty about their own infrastructure. These results should be interpreted as reflecting **participant awareness**, rather than the actual technical availability of harvesting interfaces.

Poll 2: *How familiar are you with HMC harvesting methodologies?* (single choice)

The responses suggest that familiarity with HMC harvesting methodologies is generally limited. This provides important context for the workshop discussions and helps explain why support needs, communication gaps, and expectations toward HMC emerged as recurring themes in the later breakout analysis.

Figure 5: Exposed harvesting interfaces as reported by participants.

Figure 6: Self-reported familiarity with HMC harvesting methodologies.

4.5 Breakout Session Design and Documentation

Breakout sessions were designed to enable structured reflection and balanced participation across all groups. The workshop was organized into seven breakout rooms, each with approximately four to five participants, supported by one facilitator and one designated note-taker from HMC.

Each session followed a guided process:

- Individual reflection
- Round-robin sharing
- Open discussion
- Group synthesis

Facilitators supported the discussions by encouraging equal participation, maintaining focus, and guiding groups toward agreement on key synthesis points.

To ensure consistent documentation across breakout groups, designated note-takers captured key discussion themes and agreed synthesis points rather than full transcripts. The resulting material therefore reflects structured summaries of the discussions, not verbatim records.

Each group was asked to agree on and document three synthesis points:

- One constraint or factor shaping metadata practices
- One semantic challenge or ambiguity
- One motivation or concern regarding connection to HMC services

All outputs were recorded in a shared document and used for subsequent semantic and qualitative analysis.

5 LLM-Assisted Hybrid Semantic Analysis

Following the workshop

To complement the qualitative synthesis of the breakout discussions, the documented notes were analyzed using a structured semantic approach. The aim was to identify recurring themes across breakout groups in a transparent and reproducible way, while preserving traceability to the original notes. This analysis supports interpretation of the workshop material and does not replace close reading of the discussion records.

The source material consisted of written breakout-room minutes and synthesis points. As these records summarize discussions rather than provide verbatim transcripts, they were treated as structured qualitative material. Each breakout room was analyzed as a separate unit.

A reviewed category set was developed in several steps. Initial candidate categories and representative phrases were generated with the support of large language models (LLMs) via the [Helmholtz-AI Blablador infrastructure](#), based on the workshop notes. These candidates were then manually reviewed and revised by the authors. Categories were renamed, merged, split, or removed, and example phrases refined. The final set was consolidated into three analytical perspectives aligned with the workshop design: metadata infrastructure and standards, governance and organizational responsibility, and discovery, reuse, and technical implementation.

5.1 Method

After finalizing the category set, the notes were segmented into sentence-like fragments. Each fragment was embedded semantically using sentence-transformer models and compared with the reviewed category definitions. A fragment was assigned to a category when its semantic similarity exceeded a predefined threshold; if multiple categories matched, only the best-scoring match was retained, enabling detection of semantically related formulations beyond exact wording.

Matched fragments were then classified according to evaluative orientation, distinguishing predominantly negative signals (e.g. barriers or ambiguities) from more positive signals (e.g. opportunities or support needs). The resulting counts therefore reflect both how often a theme appeared and how it was framed. Further implementation details, including model configuration, are summarized in [Table 1](#).

5.2 Findings

[Table 1](#) summarizes the workflow. The final analysis is based on 19 reviewed categories across three analytical perspectives. In total, 379 coded mentions were identified, of which 122 were classified as positive and 257 as negative. The predominance of negative signals is consistent with the workshop setting, which explicitly invited participants to articulate constraints and challenges.

Table 1: Overview of the semantic analysis workflow and resulting corpus-level counts.

Aspect	Value
Source material	Written breakout-room minutes and synthesis points
Analytical units	Individual breakout rooms and sentence-like text fragments
Initial merged category set	44 concepts
Final analytical perspectives	3
Final reviewed categories	19 total (8 + 4 + 7)
Semantic model	Sentence-transformer embeddings (all –MiniLM–L6–v2)
Concept assignment rule	Best match above cosine-similarity threshold of 0.45
Sentiment classification	Positive/negative orientation of matched fragments
Total coded mentions	379
Positive mentions	122
Negative mentions	257

In addition to the aggregate workflow metrics, Tables 2, 3, and 4 report the detailed category-level outcomes for all three analytical perspectives.

Table 2: Category-level semantic analysis results for metadata infrastructure and standards.

Category	Positive	Negative	Total	%
Incentives for metadata standardization	19	40	59	32.2%
Legacy metadata / historical constraints	6	18	24	13.1%
Need for domain-specific standards	7	17	24	13.1%
Data quality / standardization issues	4	19	23	12.6%
Resource constraints / capacity concerns	8	11	19	10.4%
ResourceType classification challenges	5	11	16	8.7%
Schema / interoperability issues	10	6	16	8.7%
Unstandardized keywords / free-text	0	2	2	1.1%
Total	59	124	183	100%

Table 3: Category-level semantic analysis results for discovery, reuse, and technical implementation.

Category	Positive	Negative	Total	%
Scientist engagement / motivation	17	21	38	30.6%
Data reuse / KPIs / indicators	11	22	33	26.6%
Centralized searchability / Knowledge Graph	3	10	13	10.5%
Identifier/PID challenges	2	11	13	10.5%
Technical debt / legacy system integration	3	9	12	9.7%
Incomplete knowledge graph coverage	3	6	9	7.3%
Complexity / overhead burden	1	5	6	4.8%
Total	40	84	124	100%

Table 4: Category-level semantic analysis results for governance, policy, and organizational responsibility.

Category	Positive	Negative	Total	%
Organizational demands tension	9	19	28	38.9%
Unclear responsibility / standards	5	20	25	34.7%
Resource constraints / responsibility gaps	8	5	13	18.1%
Field responsibility / mandatory fields	1	5	6	8.3%
Total	23	49	72	100%

5.3 Takeaways

Because the underlying material consists of summarized notes rather than full transcripts, the results should be interpreted as structured indicators of recurring themes rather than as survey-style statistics. They are useful for identifying patterns and priorities for follow-up discussion.

The workflow is reproducible once the reviewed categories and analysis settings are fixed. At the same time, the findings depend on the quality of the notes, the adequacy of the category set, and the performance of the semantic models on multilingual material. The results are therefore best understood as analytical support for interpretation, to be read together with the qualitative descriptive analysis.

6 Qualitative Descriptive Approach

This section presents the qualitative descriptive analysis of the breakout-room notes. It complements the semantic workflow described in Section 5 and supports a more grounded interpretation of the workshop material. While the semantic approach was used to detect recurring patterns

across the notes in a structured and reproducible way, the qualitative analysis was used to read the recorded discussion points more closely and interpret them in relation to the workshop questions. Together, the two approaches help explain the patterns observed in the gap analysis and provide a fuller understanding of the workshop results.

6.1 Method

The source material consisted of breakout notes that included both bullet points and full sentences. These are summaries of discussions, not verbatim transcripts.

One reviewer read the notes line by line, interpreted their meaning, and rewrote them as short statements (not full sentences) in a spreadsheet to support consistent review. A total of 65 statements were recorded. Each statement was then assigned to a subcategory based on its meaning in context rather than exact wording.

Subcategories were developed and refined iteratively. During this process, categories were edited, merged, or renamed as patterns became clearer.

In a second phase, a second reviewer independently reviewed the statements and the coding scheme. Subcategories and assignments were revised, and final assignments of statements to subcategories were agreed through discussion.

6.2 Findings

The qualitative analysis showed recurring themes across three broad areas: constraints shaping metadata practices, semantic challenges and ambiguities, and motivations and concerns regarding HMC support. In the following sections, these areas are described in more detail through specific categories and subcategories. Together, they help explain the patterns identified in the semantic analysis and add context to the metadata gaps observed in the record-based analysis.

Figure~7 shows how the coded statements are grouped into subcategories and then into the three main analytical dimensions. The figure suggests that constraint-related themes were mentioned most often, indicating that participants mainly described metadata challenges as practical and organizational issues.

The following sections describe each analytical dimension in more detail.

Constraints and Factors Shaping Metadata Practices

Across all breakout groups, constraints were the most frequently discussed aspect. Participants repeatedly referred to organizational structures, infrastructure limitations, and everyday research practices when describing metadata-related challenges. These observations help explain why the gap analysis showed persistent variation across infrastructures, especially in the use of identifiers, resource types, and date fields.

Figure 7: Distribution of coded statements across thematic labels and categories.

The most prominent constraint categories included:

- **C1 – Organizational and governance-related constraints** Competing demands between stakeholders, unclear responsibilities, and external reporting requirements shape how metadata is created and managed.
- **C2 – Technical and infrastructure limitations** Existing repository systems, limited tooling, and heterogeneous infrastructures restrict the ability to implement consistent metadata practices.
- **C3 – Resource and effort constraints** Metadata work is often manual, time-consuming, and insufficiently resourced, with coordination itself perceived as a significant effort.
- **C4 – Cultural and engagement-related barriers** Researchers are often not incentivized to provide high-quality metadata, and metadata is frequently perceived as an additional burden rather than a value-adding activity.
- **C5 – Legacy systems and heterogeneity** Historically grown metadata structures, fragmented systems, and inconsistent practices complicate integration and harmonization efforts.

Taken together, these constraints show that metadata quality is shaped not only by standards, but also by institutional responsibilities, coordination effort, and system limitations. In particular, the effort needed to align stakeholders and processes emerged as a central barrier.

Representative statements from the breakout discussions include:

“Unclear responsibility for metadata definition” (C1 – Organizational and governance constraints)

“Metadata collection is manual and individual” (C2 – Technical limitations)

“Lack of resources for metadata implementation” (C3 – Resource constraints)

“Metadata seen as effort with low value” (C4 – Cultural barriers)

“Difficulty integrating legacy metadata” (C5 – Legacy complexity)

Semantic Challenges and Ambiguities

Participants frequently described semantic challenges related to interoperability, especially in interdisciplinary and heterogeneous environments. References to inconsistent resource types, identifiers, and date formats were common. These findings help explain the patterns seen in the gap analysis, especially the use of free-text values, inconsistent identifier practices, and variation in date formats.

The most relevant categories included:

- **S1 – Missing or unclear standards** Participants reported a lack of clear guidance on which standards to apply, especially for domain-specific metadata beyond generic schemas.
- **S2 – Inconsistent terminology and free-text usage** The use of uncontrolled vocabularies and free-text fields leads to ambiguity and limits machine-readability.
- **S3 – Identifier-related issues** Missing or inconsistently applied persistent identifiers (e.g., ORCID, DOIs) hinder disambiguation and linking of entities.
- **S4 – Interoperability and schema mismatch** Differences between metadata schemas and the absence of shared crosswalks make integration across systems difficult.
- **S5 – Domain-specific complexity** Representing domain-specific metadata (e.g., experimental data, instruments, methods) within generic frameworks remains a major challenge.

These observations show that semantic inconsistencies were discussed not only as technical problems, but also as issues shaped by different practices, interpretations, and domain-specific needs.

“Generic schemas lack rich semantics” (S1 – Missing or unclear standards)

“Free-text fields without semantic control” (S2 – Inconsistent terminology)

“Missing persistent identifiers (PIDs)” (S3 – Identifier-related issues)

“Difficulty mapping domain to generic schemas” (S4 – Interoperability and schema mismatch)

“Schema mismatches require workarounds” (S4 – Interoperability and schema mismatch)

“Lack of understanding of domain-specific metadata” (S5 – Domain-specific complexity)

Motivations and Concerns Regarding HMC Integration

Participants described both strong interest in and reservations about engagement with HMC services. Their statements referred to support needs, expectations about communication and prioritization, and questions about how harmonization activities should be implemented in practice. These findings add context to both the semantic analysis and the gap analysis by showing what kinds of support participants expect and what concerns they have about implementation.

The material also shows that motivations and concerns were closely linked. Participants did not simply ask for more standardization in the abstract. Rather, they pointed to specific areas in which HMC support could be useful, while also making clear that such support must remain practical, domain-sensitive, and realistic in relation to local constraints.

The main categories included:

- **M1 – Need for guidance and training** Participants emphasized the need for practical orientation on responsibilities, priorities, and domain-specific metadata standards.
- **M2 – Need for standards and harmonization** There is clear interest in Helmholtz-wide coordination, but with room for layered and domain-sensitive approaches.
- **M3 – Need for tools and infrastructure support** Participants highlighted the need for workflows and tools that reduce effort and better support metadata work beyond publication-centric processes.
- **M4 – Desire for improved discovery and reuse** Expected benefits include better access, more transparent reuse conditions, and stronger linking of metadata across systems.
- **M5 – Expectations regarding HMC’s role and visibility** Participants called for clearer communication about HMC services, responsibilities, and support capacity.

Taken together, these categories show that participants were interested in HMC support, but expected it to be practical, clearly communicated, and sensitive to local contexts. They asked for guidance and training, better tools and workflows, and more support for harmonization and reuse. At the same time, they raised concerns about visibility, capacity, and the limits of generic solutions.

Representative statements from the breakout discussions include:

“Need clearer responsibility (e.g. ORCID, PIDINST)” (M1 – Need for guidance and training)

“Need guidance on domain-specific metadata standards” (M1 – Need for guidance and training)

“Desire for Helmholtz-wide adoption of standards” (M2 – Need for standards and harmonization support)

“Need better tools and incentives” (M3 – Need for tools and infrastructure)

“Interest in knowledge graphs and linked data” (M4 – Desire for improved discovery and reuse)

“Limited awareness of HMC services” (M5 – Expectations regarding HMC’s role and visibility)

Taken together, these responses show that participants were not only pointing to problems. They were also expressing concrete expectations and a willingness to engage. Across the report, the gap analysis shows where metadata gaps appear, while the workshop findings help explain the practical and organizational reasons behind them. This suggests that HMC support will be most useful when it is practical, clearly communicated, and responsive to institutional and domain-specific needs.

7 From Insights to Action: Next Steps

Building on the presented HMC services, the gap analysis, and the community input, several concrete next steps were identified.

7.1 Individual Consulting Phase

Given the diversity of infrastructures and the challenges identified, HMC will offer one-on-one consulting sessions to address institution-specific needs.

These sessions will:

- Provide a confidential and structured space to discuss individual requirements and priorities
- Include a 60-minute session to review institution-specific metadata snapshots
- Facilitate discussion of interpretations and constraints
- Conclude with agreement on one to three realistic and actionable next steps

7.2 Continued Metadata Review and Feedback Integration

TF Harmony will continue reviewing metadata harvested from provider endpoints to identify recurring patterns, structural challenges, and opportunities for improvement.

This ongoing analysis will be complemented by insights from the one-on-one consulting sessions. Feedback from these sessions will be documented and synthesized to capture both common challenges and emerging good practices across infrastructures.

Participants will receive a summary of their individual sessions, and follow-up meetings can be arranged where needed. These follow-ups are considered an important and practical mechanism to support continued exchange and progress.

All individual discussions will remain strictly confidential. No institute-level information will be shared.

7.3 Follow-Up Workshop

Aggregated and anonymized insights from the metadata analysis and consulting sessions will be presented and discussed at a follow-up workshop on 28 April 2026 in Heidelberg, held as a pre-conference event of the HMC Conference 2026.

The workshop will focus on cross-cutting challenges, shared experiences, and emerging success stories, providing a basis for continued alignment and collaboration across Helmholtz infrastructures.

7.4 Recommendations

Building on the gap analysis, the workshop discussions, and the planned next steps, the following recommendations highlight priority areas where targeted support and coordinated action can most effectively improve metadata interoperability across Helmholtz infrastructures.

- **Strengthen PID adoption through clear workflows** Identifiers are widely present, but persistent identifiers (e.g. DOIs, ORCID) are used inconsistently. Focus on clarifying responsibilities, integration points, and workflows for PID assignment and maintenance.
- **Provide practical semantic guidance for core fields** Fields such as dc:type, dc: identifier , and dc:date show recurring inconsistencies. Provide clear guidance on controlled vocabularies, recommended formats (e.g. ISO 8601), and field usage, with Helmholtz-relevant examples.
- **Develop and maintain transparent schema crosswalks** Interoperability is limited by schema differences and local implementations. Support versioned crosswalks (e.g. DataCite–Dublin Core), including documentation of mapping decisions and known limitations.
- **Enable domain-specific extensions within a shared framework** Generic schemas are often insufficient. Support layered approaches that combine harmonized core metadata with domain-specific extensions.
- **Reduce manual effort through tooling and workflows** Metadata curation is resource-intensive. Prioritize tools for semi-automated enrichment, validation, and quality checks that integrate with existing systems.
- **Improve visibility and clarity of HMC services** Awareness of HMC services and harvesting processes remains limited. Strengthen communication of available services, responsibilities, and support formats.

- **Adopt a consulting-based, center-specific support model** Given heterogeneous infrastructures, one-size-fits-all approaches are ineffective. Use one-on-one consulting to address local constraints and define realistic next steps.
- **Strengthen incentives and feedback loops for metadata quality** Improve researcher engagement by linking metadata quality to visibility, reuse, and reporting outcomes (e.g. FAIR Data Dashboard, Helmholtz KG).
- **Continue iterative analysis and feedback integration** Treat harmonization as an ongoing process. Combine continuous metadata analysis with structured feedback from consulting and follow-up workshops to track progress and refine support.

8 Conclusion

The workshop demonstrated both the diversity of metadata practices across Helmholtz infrastructures and the shared interest in improving consistency and interoperability.

By combining technical analysis with community input, the workshop provided a foundation for more targeted and collaborative approaches to metadata harmonization. The planned next steps, including individualized consulting and continued engagement, will support this process and contribute to the development of more FAIR and interoperable metadata across Helmholtz.

9 Appendix

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